

METHODS AND EXPERIENCES OF TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation

Currently, disputes about the advantages and disadvantages of foreign and local methods of teaching English are not subsiding. Criticism of traditional techniques has become the rule of good tone in modern Russian education. By the standards of many experts, traditional approaches to learning the language are too boring both in terms of conducting classes and in content. In this article we will consider the advantages of TBE (Teachers of Business English) proposed by LTTC (London Pedagogical College) and materials of the Longman Teacher Development.

Keywords: inner translation; the listening technique; facial expression; The Freeze Method.

Introduction

The experience of teaching the English language given by experts-native speakers is the major factor. Nowadays one of the key issues in this process is its effective introduction and use in the modern programs, including the federal ones. Nowadays a debate about the advantages and disadvantages of foreign and local methods of teaching English is still taking place. Traditional methods are widely criticized [1-3]. Many specialists consider the traditional approaches to learning a foreign language too boring. Training based on traditional methods is considered to take too much time, that is why a lot of students do not complete it. Moreover, it does not give learners an opportunity to "immerse" in the language environment and to overcome the barrier of "inner translation" [4-7]. However, even if this well-reasoned criticism is taken into account, it is impossible to ignore the main advantage of using the traditional methods – gradual acquisition of fundamental, basic knowledge, application of which will be long-term one. As practice shows, the use

of traditional approaches and methods in combination with communicative and humanistic ones provides the most effective training [8-11].

The main part

The activities are very significant since they help the student become more aware of linguistic subtleties. These are currently the most effective methods for fixing errors:

1. The temporal framework (a timeline). The instructor illustrates the temporal frame at which the English
2. The technique using the fingers. This is frequently the listening technique that uses the finger image, which is no longer specified.
3. The facial expression and gesture approach is similar to the finger method; however, in this instance, the instructor uses alternative gestures or expressions to point out an error.
4. Mistakes in purchases across the board. Every pupil locates and fixes their own fault on their own.
5. The Freeze Method. Put an end to the mistake and fix it.

This technique, however, should not always be used, but only to correct often repeated errors (Fossilized errors) and pronunciation (Pronunciation Errors), since the frequent “stop” of the student slows down the development of speaking skills.

6. Work with often repeated errors. An expert is appointed - a student who has this problem, he will have to find and correct such errors.

Most often, these errors are associated with the use of the end of –S in the form of 3 persons the only number, the production of articles, the correct structure of Conditionals. The systematic language of teaching the language according to this method is built in such a way that its center is the word. The word is studied at the level of its structure (Word Formation, Prefixes and Suffixes), its use (Word use), including in idioms and metaphors, in lexical and grammatical contexts, that is, at the level of at least phrases or text [12-15].

The most successful methods for learning a word include associative perception (number one), visual perception, rhyming repetition when needed, word development within the context of existing grammar and vocabulary, memory exams, and application in speech. The phrase indicates that the word repetition is a prolonged process of learning rather than just mechanical multiple duplication; First day: the student is introduced to the new vocabulary; second day: it is repeated

within 10 minutes; seventh day: it is repeated within 5 minutes; and after a month: it is repeated within 2-4 minutes.

It is essential to use as many of the specified exercise kinds as you can in order to effectively memorize the term. The four basic routes of language development (Skills Development) are followed when studying vocabulary: passive, receptive (reading and listening); active, productive (speaking and writing). English language study should be approached in the following order, according to British experts: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. We highlight the salient features of the methods used to investigate these facets. It is advised that hearing be learned in conjunction with reading, and that one should follow the following plan of action: 1. Announcing the subject; 2. The image is presented alongside the text; 3. A description of the process by which abilities grow as one listens to the text; 4. Choosing terms that are unknown to you before the hearing starts; 5. Using the text as a guide to help you perform the necessary action; 6. An explanation that the key to listening effectively is to grasp the text's core idea, rather than trying to cover every detail. When instructing speech, the following should be taken into consideration: The learner should be engaged with the subject matter and method according to their age; 2) Pair work should be ensured; 3) Different tasks should be assigned; and 4) Practice describing objects or images. In the event that kids are nonver

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